

Kinetics of Non-isothermal Decomposition of [Co(NH₃)₅X]Br₂ Complexes with X = Cl, Br or I Atoms

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The mechanisms of the non-isothermal decomposition of [Co(NH₃)₅X]Br₂ complexes with X = Cl, Br or I atoms are reported together with the determination of the kinetic parameters Z , E , ΔH and ΔS by non-isothermal methods. The complexes decomposed in well defined steps and the mechanisms by which decomposition took place have been manifested. The TG, DTG and DSC of the various complexes were taken under N₂ as well as O₂ atmosphere. The enhancement effect of O₂ gas on the decomposition steps has been interpreted.

TG, DTG and DSC methods have become very popular and widely used for characterisation of various phases, transformation and decomposition reactions. Transition metals have been used in the preparation of different widely applied complexes¹. Among these complexes is halogenopenta-amminecobalt(III) complexes [Co(NH₃)₅X]²⁺, where X can be Cl, Br or I atoms. The electronic transitions between orbitals that are centred on different atoms depend on the type of X where these bands appear at progressively lower frequencies on going from chloro to the bromo to the iodo complex, as one might expect from the trend in reduction potentials for these halogens.

A perusal of the literature² reveals, however, that most of the work that has been done on the thermal properties of these compounds is not deep in nature for describing their modes of decomposition, thermal stability and investigating the kinetics and mechanisms by which they are decomposed. Hence, as a part of investigations of the thermal behaviour on decomposition the kinetics of the non-isothermal decomposition of these complexes is reported.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

Several equations³ have been proposed for analysing a TG-curve and obtaining values of kinetic parameters. The rate of a decomposition process can

be described as the product of two separate functions of temperature and conversion⁴ using equation,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T) f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found / (Calcd.)		
	Co	N	H
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Cl]Br ₂	17.12	21.18	4.31
	(17.38)	20.64	4.46)
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Br]Br ₂	15.04	18.46	3.83
	(15.37)	18.25	3.95)
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ I]Br ₂	13.34	16.43	3.64
	(13.69)	16.26	3.52)

where the function $k(T)$ is temperature-dependent and $f(\alpha)$ is the conversion dependent on the mechanism of the reaction. It has been established⁵ that the temperature-dependent function $k(T)$ is of the Arrhenius type and can be written as

$$k = A e^{-E/RT} \quad (2)$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor, E the activation energy and R the gas constant. Combining equations (1) and (2) we get,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = (A/q) e^{-E/RT} f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

where $q = dT/dt$ is the linear heating rate. On integration and approximation, equation (3) becomes

$$\ln g(\alpha) = -E/RT + \ln AR/qE \quad (4)$$

To fit the thermal decomposition data into the various models, a Lotus macroprogram was used for obtaining

R^2 values as well as linear kinetic equations. Since model equation (4) could be represented as

$$y = a + bx \quad (5)$$

the regression value R^2 is given by the form,

$$R^2 = \frac{[\sum xy - n\bar{x}\bar{y}]^2}{[\sum x^2 - n\bar{x}^2][\sum y^2 - n\bar{y}^2]} \quad (6)$$

On applying this procedure, the regression line having a value of R^2 nearest to unity is selected. The values of E and A have been calculated and the entropy change ΔS was calculated using the equation⁶,

$$\Delta S = R \ln(Ah/kT_s) \quad (7)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and h is the Plank constant.

TABLE 2—KINETIC EQUATIONS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE SIMULATED DECOMPOSITION REACTION

Mechanism	$g(\alpha)$	Rete-controlling process
D_1	α^2	One dimensional diffusion
D_2	$\alpha + (1 - \alpha) \ln(1 - \alpha)$	Two-dimensional diffusion
D_3	$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{3/2}]^2$	Three-dimensional diffusion (Jander function)
D_4	$(1 - 2\alpha/3) - (1 - \alpha)^{3/2}$	Three-dimensional diffusion (Ginstling - Brounshtein function)
R_n	$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/n}]$	Phase boundary reaction $n = 1, 2$ and 3
A_m	$[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/m}$	Random nucleation and its subsequent growth $m = 2$ and 3 (Avrami-Erfafeev function)
F_1	$\ln(1 - \alpha)$	First order kinetics

In order to test the validity of the above considerations we have constructed the TG curves corresponding to the different mechanism listed in Table 2. The TG, DTG and DSC for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Br}_2$ are shown in Fig. 1. The complex undergoes decomposition with loss of ligands with the formation of the metal as the final product when N_2 gas was used, and metal oxide when O_2 gas was used as decomposition media. The TG weight-loss at each temperature is recorded in

Fig. 1. TG, DTG and DSC curves for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Br}_2$.

Table 3, with the corresponding fragment that can be decomposed.

Comparing the total % loss found and that expected, it appears that there is a difference of 11.46% which is corresponding to a retention of one chlorine atom into the solid lattice up to 950° where it is transferred from coordination type to an ionic state. This is

confirmed by decomposing $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ under the same experimental conditions and it was found that the compound sustained the heating effect up to this temperature.

the three-dimensional diffusion-controlled (D_3) together with the three-dimensional diffusion-controlled (D_4). The activation energies calculated are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 3—TG DATA FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Br}_2$ IN (a) N_2 AND (b) O_2 ATMOSPHERE

Flow Rate = 50 ml NTP/min

Fragment decomposed	% Loss Found		TG maximum temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
5 mol $\text{NH}_3 + 0.19$ mol Br	29.37	29.41	255.3	256.3
0.5 mol Br	11.75	9.96	467.3	346.3
1.23 mol Br	28.92	2.03	620	422
0.09 mol Br	2.13	33.14	656	501
Total % loss	72.17	74.54		
Theoretical % loss expected 83.63.				

The DSC thermogram of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Br}_2$ shows an endothermic peak at 265° followed instantly by two exothermic peaks located at 300° and 370° . At 460° an endothermic peak exists. The first endothermic peak corresponds to evolution of 5 NH_3 molecules followed by Br-gas evolution in two exothermic peaks. The final endothermic one is mainly due to rearrangement of the final lattice residue together with evolution of the remaining Br atoms.

TABLE 4—KINETIC PARAMETERS CALCULATED BY ANALYSIS OF α -VALUES CORRESPONDING TO THE DECOMPOSITION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Br}_2$ ACCORDING TO THE MECHANISMS SHOWN IN TABLE 2

$g(\alpha)$ employed	E kJ mol^{-1}	A s^{-1}	
D_1	107.4	1.2×10^6	0.993 6
D_2	111.9	1.3×10^6	0.993 5
D_3	114.4	1.19×10^6	0.995 5
D_4	112.6	1.16×10^6	0.994 5
$R_{n=1}$	50.7	5.8×10^5	0.992 6
$R_{n=2}$	52.5	6.26×10^5	0.992 6
$R_{n=3}$	53.1	6.7×10^5	0.992 5
$A_{m=2}$	52.7	2.1×10^5	0.990 0
$A_{m=3}$	49.9	0.7×10^5	0.986 2
F_1	60.9	1.2×10^6	0.992 4

Data obtained from the non-isothermal TG experiment were analysed as α -values (fraction decomposed) according to the functions listed in Table 2, and the results show that the best-fit of data is obtained with

Fig. 2. TG, DTG and DSC curves for $(\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br})\text{Br}_2$.

When oxygen gas was used as decomposition atmosphere, an enhancement effect was achieved either for TG or DSC thermograms as shown in Fig. 1. From Table 3, it appears that there is no pronounced

effect of using O₂ atmosphere on the first TG decomposition peak. This fact reflects that at this temperature the diffusion rate of O₂ into the lattice defects is small. On increasing the TG temperature an enhancement effect of the decomposition rate to a lower temperature was observed.

When the coordinated Cl atoms were replaced by Br and thermally decomposed, different effects were observed as shown in Table 5 or Fig. 2.

TABLE 5—TG DATA FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF [Co(NH₃)₅Br]Br₂ IN (a) N₂ AND (b) O₂ ATMOSPHERE

Flow Rate = 50 ml NTP/min

Fragment	% loss found		Tg maximum temp (°C)	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
decomposed				
1.65 ± 2 mol	27.29	27.41	260	257
NH ₃ + 1 mol Br				
3 mol NH ₃	12.08	11.99	377	372
1.8 mol Br	37.50	38.67	584	465
Total % loss found	76.07	78.07		

Theoretical total % loss expected 84.65.

As indicated in Table 5, the TG peaks assigned were corresponding to the liberation of the indicated fragments. When the TG data were analysed according to the functions listed in Table 2, the results show that the best-fit of data are obtained with D₁, D₂, D₃ and D₄ decomposition with an activation energies listed in Table 6.

TABLE 6—KINETIC PARAMETERS CALCULATED BY ANALYSING OF α-VALUES CORRESPONDING TO THE DECOMPOSITION OF [Co(NH₃)₅Br]Br₂ ACCORDING TO THE MECHANISMS SHOWN IN TABLE 2

g(α) employed	E kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	r
D ₁	34.9	1.29 × 10 ⁶	0.996 4
D ₂	35.3	1.36 × 10 ⁶	0.996 4
D ₃	13.9	1.65 × 10 ⁵	0.996 4
D ₄	6.4	3.8 × 10 ⁵	0.996 4
R _{n=1}	36.0	1.54 × 10 ⁵	0.995 5
R _{n=2}	76.3	6.67 × 10 ⁵	0.995 6
R _{n=3}	77.5	3.26 × 10 ⁵	0.995 6
A _{m=2}	82.8	0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.992 9
A _{m=3}	77.8	0.75 × 10 ⁵	0.986 4
F ₁	33.9	3.3 × 10 ⁵	0.995 6

When O₂ gas was used as decomposition atmosphere, the first TG peak was not affected while the rest

Fig. 3. TG, DTG and DSC curves for [Co(NH₃)₅I]Br₂.

were enhanced to lower decomposition temperatures. The DSC thermogram (Fig. 2) indicates an endothermic peak at first, followed by exothermic peaks with different intensities according to the process taking place. Finally, when the coordinated halogen atom was substituted with I atoms into the complex coordination

sphere $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}]\text{Br}_2$ and thermally decomposed, another different thermal behaviour was observed (Fig. 3). The TG data are listed in Table 7. The TG and DTG thermograms manifest that I atoms are loosely bounded in the coordination sphere due to its large volume compared with Cl and Br atoms. Therefore, their removal was at earlier stages, i.e. 234° . When O_2 was used as decomposition atmosphere, the complex decomposed completely at lower temperature of 395° . The reason could be due to the high concentration of anion vacancies facilitating the diffusion process. This idea is supported when different kinetic model functions listed in Table 2 are examined. The comparison of fits given in Table 8 shows that the best correlation coefficient is obtained by D_1 and D_2 mechanisms beside D_3 and D_4 mechanisms.

TABLE 7—TG DATA FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}]\text{Br}_2$ IN (a) N_2 AND (b) O_2 ATMOSPHERE

Flow Rate = 50 ml NTP / min

Fragment decomposed	% loss found		TG maximum temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
$3\text{NH}_3 + \text{I}$	41.54	43.65	234	229
2NH_3	4.97	5.23	324	311
(a) 1.55 Br	28.75		568	
(b) 1.75 Br		32.47		395
Total % loss found	75.26	81.35		
Theoretical total % loss expected 86.32.				

The DSC thermogram of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}]\text{Br}_2$ (Fig. 3) was examined. A thermal decomposition endothermic peak was followed by an exothermic one. The feature for these peaks are different than those for the chloro and the bromo complexes when the exothermic peak came retarded by about 40° after the first endothermic peak.

TABLE 8—KINETIC PARAMETERS CALCULATED BY ANALYSIS OF α -VALUES CORRESPONDING TO THE DECOMPOSITION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}]\text{Br}_2$ ACCORDING TO THE MECHANISMS SHOWN IN TABLE 2

$g(\alpha)$ employed	E kJ mol^{-1}	$10^5 A$ s^{-1}	r
D_1	77.3	4.87	0.998 9
D_2	79.8	5.08	0.996 7
D_3	82.5	4.3	0.996 5

Table 8 (contd.)

D_4	80.7	3.41	0.996 7
$R_{n=1}$	35.0	2.95	0.996 2
$R_{n=2}$	36.5	3.16	0.996 0
$R_{n=3}$	56.6	4.64	0.995 9
$\lambda_{m=2}$	43.4	1.21	0.993 8
$\lambda_{m=3}$	44.4	6.68	0.990 2
F_1	47.7	6.60	0.995

The enthalpy change (ΔH) accompanied by the thermal decomposition of the complexes in the early stages of decomposition shows the energy gap between the original structure and its activated state. The values obtained from the DSC measurements are shown in Table 9.

TABLE 9—ENTHALPY CHANGE ΔH FOR THE EARLY STAGES OF DECOMPOSITION OF THE COMPLEXES AND ITS MAXIMUM DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE UNDER N_2 ATMOSPHERE

Compd.	ΔH J g^{-1}	ΔS $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	Max temp. $^\circ\text{C}$
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$	860.5	-134.10	267.7
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$	637.9	-132.44	273
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{I}]\text{Br}_2$	586.8	-140.78	255

In spite of the ΔH values of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ being higher than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$, the entropy change of the first one has a little negative value than the latter. This can be attributed to the fact that migration of the coordination Cl atom from a covalent position to an ionic can facilitate the decomposition of the complex; this is documented when the DSC maximum temperature 267.7° is compared with 273° for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ ion. The ΔS values obtained for the complexes for the first step of decomposition are negative which indicates that the activated complex has a more ordered structure than the reactant at that decomposition temperature.

In conclusion, the weight-loss data agree that diffusion of the produced gases is the rate-controlling step in the decomposition. Thus the most probable step controlling the rate of decomposition of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}]^{2+}$ is the transfer of electrons from the coordinated atoms and molecules to Co^{2+} ions. Also the

anion vacancies are known to act as electron traps⁷ and, hence, can act as potential nucleus forming sites in electron transfer processes. This appears to be the reason for the observed diversity of decomposition when Cl was replaced by Br or I atoms.

Experimental

The halogenopenta-amminecobalt(III) complexes were prepared and purified according to the reported methods⁸. The concentration of the metal ion was determined using a Varian AA-1475 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were obtained using a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser.

TG and DTG thermograms were recorded using a TA-300 Mettler thermobalance with a heating rate of $10^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$, taking 10 mg sample. The TG or DSC cell was fed with $50 \text{ ml NTP min}^{-1} \text{ N}_2$ or O_2 in the temperature range $50\text{--}950^{\circ}$. The DSC analyser used was a Mettler DSC-30 system with the conditions as in TG analysis except that final temperature was 590° and the

weight of sample 6 mg. TG data were obtained using a Lotus 1-2-3 program, Development Corporation 1989 and Energraphic Program Copyright 1983, Enertronics Research Inc. and PS/2 30 IBM computer.

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